

SIMILARITY MEASUREMENTS OF CANDIDATE'S ANSWERS TO MARATHI QA SYSTEM

BHARAT A. SHELKE*

Research Fellow, Dept. of Computer Science & IT Dr. B. A. M. University, Aurangabad, India.
Email: bashelke@gmail.com

C. NAMRATA MAHENDER

Assistant Professor, Dept. of Computer Science & IT Dr. B. A. M. University Aurangabad, India.
Email: cnamrata.csit@bamu.ac.in

Abstract

Question Answering is becoming into a significant topic of research for researchers as there is an increasingly high level of technological advancement. Data is available in large amounts on the internet. People have become interested in searching for their needs on Internet, as it is the simplest way of gaining information with a click. QA systems are essential in education. Which has been provided during the Covid-19 pandemic as online education becomes the generic way of teaching-learning. There are two types of question-answering systems: closed - domain and open-domain. The best approach to get answers to user questions which are asked in natural language as compared to a query is through question answering. Popular languages spoken in India include Hindi, Punjabi, Telugu, Bengali, Malayalam, and others. These languages are now being researched extensively and taken into consideration by researchers. Currently, these languages are taken into consideration by the researchers and a lot of work is being done on these languages. During our study, Comparing the Marathi language to other Indian languages, we found that relatively little study has been done in the Indian context. In this study, a method for evaluating the system performance is presented. It is intended to examine how closely the candidate's paraphrased answers to the model answer match up with our model answers.

Keywords: Question, Answer, Question Answering System, NLP

1. INTRODUCTION

Text similarity measurement, a crucial task for natural language processing, is used in some means of determining the degree of semantic similarity between two texts. Text duplication detection, information retrieval, the automatic creation of text areas, and text classification are just a few of the numerous areas in which text similarity measures are used extensively. The entire text is treated as a group of words in the statistical text-similarity measuring approach. The text model vector is produced in terms of effective word frequency information by examining the number of occurrences of each phrase. Furthermore, the similarities of text vectors are determined using cosine similarity or the Jaccard coefficient. Statistics technique includes models based on attribute theory, semantic index models, and vector space models. For statistical similarity assessment, it expresses the text as a vector to simplify the complex relationship between the keywords in the text, allowing the model to be readily calculated. [Zhang, H. et al (2021)]. The semantic relationship of text words (e.g., synonymy, redundancy, and inclusion) is created by specified domain knowledge for the text-similarity measurement method based on semantic analysis. [Li, C. (2021)], Measures of

various semantic similarity techniques have been proposed over the past three decades. Most scholars divide text similarity measurement methods based on statistics or corpus and knowledge bases [Gomaa, W. H. et al (2020)] [Wang, Jiapeng (2020)]. Our work is concerned with the closed domain QA system. In this research work, we are developing a Marathi corpus for answer retrieval for the QA system. We have created model answers and answers are collected from candidates. Here we have represented the procedure for text similarity between model answers with the different candidate answers.

2. QUESTION AND ANSWER

2.1 Question

The question, the word, never needs a dictionary to know, but the response sometimes requires searching the entire world for just a response. A question is a noun sentence that is recorded or expressed in order to elicit information. [Lidy, e. D. (2001)].

2.2 Types of Questions [Khillare, S. A. et al (2014)]

- (1) Factoid-Based Questions: Factoid-based questions have a single fact as the answer. For example, when was Subhash Chandra born?
- (2) Definition Questions: The answer should be a short paragraph that briefly wishes to know features of the thing, such as a person's birth date, height.
- (3) True- False Questions: are those that have a simple yes or no answer. e.g. Is pollution worse in Mumbai than in Pune?
- (4) Instruction-Based Questions: These are questions that provide directions, such as "How do I make piza?"
- (5) Explanation Questions: These are questions that require an explanation, such as "Why did America enter WWII?"
- (6) List Questions: are those questions in which there is an answer is in list format.

2.3 Answer

The answer is a noun, which is something stated or done in response to, or as a reaction to, a statement or situation. An answer to a specific question may utilize more than one mode of expression. As a result, the responses are customized to each user's specific needs.

3. REVIEW ON QUESTION ANSWERING SYSTEM

The foundation of TREC has encouraged Indians to push for work in their native language. Some researchers in question answering systems shifted their focus from worldwide languages like English, Japanese, and Chinese to Indian regional languages like Tamil, Punjabi, Bengali, Malayalam, Hindi, and so on. While researching the works of authors, it was discovered that Marathi language work is very basic in comparison to other languages. [Khillare, S. A. et al (2014)]. Sahu, Shriya, N. Vashnik, and Devshri Roy [Sahu, S. et al.

(2012)] provided a method for extracting answers from Hindi text for a given question in which the text is expressed in the form of query logic language and then the relevant answer for the given question is extracted. The approach has primarily focused on four types of questions: What, Where, How Many, and What Time. A shallow parser was used to extract the type of query and keywords, but no semantic relations were examined when extracting information. The majority of QA systems are built using a linguistic approach. Vasnik et al. [Vasnik, N. et al. (2012)] offer TALASH, a Hindi search engine. Using similarity heuristics based on locality. Kumar, Praveen, and colleagues [Kumar, P. (2003)] developed a Hindi search engine. It allows you to extract linked content from a set of e-learning contents. The architecture includes an entity generator that produces particular domain entities. Such generated entities matched the queries that users intended to find answers for. The suitable answers were then chosen after classifying the questions the users had submitted. Words are taken out of the query stop, and relevant keywords are extracted. Synonyms for the keywords in the query were added. The retrieval engine receives the query and, after ranking the passages, returns the top ones based on the location. The Hindi QAS system was developed by Stalin, Shalini, Rajeev Pandey, and Raju Barskar [Shalini, S. et al. (2012)] and is based on a context-based search using the similarity heuristic and partial semantic and syntactic data. Here, a database is utilized to transmit a collection of candidate answers, based on the keywords in the query, to the subsequent answer extraction module, which extracts candidate answers from the documents that were retrieved. V. Gupta suggests using a question-answering system to generate an answer in Punjabi [Gupta V. (2013)]. The system accepts questions in Punjabi, where the stop word is originally removed. Then, using the Punjabi dictionary, essential words such as nouns, adjectives, verbs, or adverbs are extracted from the query string. With the help of the extracted keywords and their synonyms, a query is finally reformulated. Using a reformulated query, a search engine retrieves multiple matching web pages. The extracted documents are summarized based on the proximity of important terms identified in the papers, and the candidate's answer is provided depending on their rank. P. Gupta and V. Gupta propose an algorithm for the Punjabi Question Answering System [Gupta, P. et al. (2013)]. The system offers a more effective method for discovering patterns and matching to obtain accurate precise answers from a set of possible answers. The proposed algorithm works for (what), _(when), (where), (who), and (why) form of questions, where the first question word is extracted from the question, then matching question keywords are extracted and final answers are retrieved using distinct procedures created for each question type. The overall accuracy of the system is 73 percent, with 4850 questions asked for over 50 documents in Punjabi language Keyword-based question answering system is developed by J. Cherapanamjeri, et al. [Cherapanamjeri, J. (2014)]. This is an answer to a question about agricultural statistics in Telugu. All of the keywords in the user query are mapped to the database, and if the keyword matches, relevant SQL queries are generated to retrieve answers from the database. R. Reddy, N. Reddy, and S. Bandyopadhyay present a dialogue-based Question Answering System that offers responses pertaining to the railway domain in Telugu.[Reddy, R. (2006)].The Question Answering process is based on a keyword approach, in which input queries are tokenized and keywords are extracted using a railway knowledge base. Bharat A. Shelkeet. al. [Shelke B. et al. (2019)] took a survey of QA

systems developed in Indian regional Languages, only limited work is done in Indian regional languages but no work in Marathi Language.

4. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

In this proposed work, explanation regarding the procedure for similarity measurement of the model answer with the candidate answers. This procedure explains the steps involved in the measurement of similarity between model answers and candidate answers as shown in Figure

Figure 1: Procedure steps in Similarity measurement of candidate's answers

Table 1: Class Wise Questions and Chapters

Class	Questions	Chapters
Class – II	401	23
Class – III	212	09
Class – IV	288	10
Total	901	42

4.3 Model Question Answer Database

For model Question answer database creation, we selected only two (02) chapters from each class and designed ten (10) questions for each chapter. There are six (06) chapters and sixty (60) questions designed for the model database. Model question answers are stored in

the 'mod_ans' database. Questions are framed and then referred to the subject experts for spelling and grammar mistakes. Some sample question answers are shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Sample of Model Question Answer Database

Q	Model Question	Model Answer
१	शाळेतकशाच्या स्पर्धा झाल्या होत्या?	शाळेतचित्रकला, रांगोळी, कथाकथन स्पर्धा झाल्या होत्या
२	शाळेतकशाचा समारंभ होता?	शाळेतबक्षीस समारंभ होता
३	शाळेतीलसमारंभासाठी कोणाला आमंत्रण दिले होते?	शाळेतीलसमारंभासाठी मुलांना आणि त्यांच्या पालकांना आमंत्रण दिले होते
४	मुग्धा वतिचे आईबाबा कोठे जाऊन बसले?	मुग्धा वतिचे आईबाबा खुर्चीत जाऊन बसले
५	मुग्धाच्याआई व बाबा ने शाळेत कोणाची भेट घेतली?	मुग्धाच्याआई व बाबा ने शाळेत बाईची भेट घेतली
६	बाईनेमुग्धा बद्दल काय सांगितले?	बाईनेमुग्धा अभ्यासात हुशार आहे असे सांगितले
७	चित्रकलेच्यास्पर्धेत पहिल्या नंबरचे बक्षीस कोण पटकावला होता?	चित्रकलेच्यास्पर्धेत पहिल्या नंबरचे बक्षीस मुग्धाने पटकावला होता
८	मुग्धाचास्वभाव कसा होता?	मुग्धाचास्वभाव शांत होता
९	मुग्धा वतिचे आई बाबा कोठे जाऊन बसले?	मुग्धा वतिचे आई बाबा खुर्चीत जाऊन बसले
१०	कार्यक्रमाचेप्रमुख पाहुणे कोण होते?	कार्यक्रमाचेप्रमुख पाहुणे एक प्रसिद्ध लेखक आले होते

4.4 Question Classification

We are work on fifty (50) types of question in Marathi Language such as कधी, कशाची, काय, कुठे, कॅव्हाetc. [Shelke B. (2021)]. These question types are shown in Table 3.

Table 3: Question Classifications

कधी	करीत	कशल्या	कशा	कोणी	कोठून	कोणता	कोणाचा
कशाची	कशाचे	कश्याच्या	कशात	कोणासोबत	कोणती	कोणाकडून	
कशानी	कशाने	कशापासून	कशामुळे	कोणासारखे	कोणा	कोणाची	
कशाला	कशावर	कशासाठी	कशी	कोणासाठी	कोठे	कोणाजवळ	
कसली	कसा	कसे	का	कोणाला	कोणते	कोणाच्या	
काय	कायम	कितवा	कितवी	कोणामध्ये	कोणाकडे	कोणाचे	
कितती	कुठे	कुणी	कॅव्हा	कोणाबद्दल	कोण	कोणत्या	

4.5 Similarity & Evaluation Measures

The similarity measure evaluates how similar two data objects are. In a data-mining context, the similarity measure is a distance with dimensions representing object features. A small distance indicates a high degree of similarity, whereas a large distance indicates a low degree of similarity. The similarity is subjective and depends heavily on the domain and application. For example, two fruits may be identical in color, size, or flavour. When computing distance between unrelated dimensions/features, exercise extreme caution. Each element's relative values must be normalized, or else one characteristic may wind up dominating the distance calculation. Similarities are measured on a scale of 0 to 1 [0, 1].

4.5.1 Sequence Matcher Percentage

Sequence Matcher is a type of class. It compares two input sequences or strings. In other words, this class is useful for detecting character-level similarities between two strings. The sequence matcher's goal is to take two sequences and find the length of the longest subsequence in both of them.

4.5.2 Cosine Similarity [Dice, L.R. (1945)]

Cosine similarity is the similarity between two vectors in an inner product space that measures the cosine of the angle between them.

$$\text{Similarity} = \cos \theta = \frac{A \cdot B}{\|A\| \|B\|} = \frac{\sum_{t=1}^n A_t \cdot B_t}{\sqrt{\sum_{t=1}^n A_t^2} \cdot \sqrt{\sum_{t=1}^n B_t^2}} \quad (1)$$

The normalised dot product of the two attributes is determined by the Cosine similarity metric. We would basically try to find the cosine of the angle between the two objects by determining the cosine similarity. The cosine of 0° is one, whereas any other angle has a cosine smaller than one. It is thus an orientation judgement rather than a magnitude decision: two vectors with the same orientation have a cosine similarity of 1, two vectors at 90° have a similarity of 0, and two diametrically opposing vectors have a similarity of -1, regardless of magnitude. Cosine similarity is especially useful in positive space, since the result is neatly bounded in $[0, 1]$. One of the reasons for cosine similarity's popularity is that it is very simple.

4.5.3 Jaccard Similarity [Jaccard, P. (1901)]

The number of common terms in each string is multiplied by the number of unique terms to get Jaccard similarity. In which the objects are either points or vectors. These items will be sets when we evaluate Jaccard similarity. The cardinality of the intersection of sets divided by the cardinality of the union of the sample sets is used to calculate the Jaccard similarity between finite sample sets. If you want to find the Jaccard similarity between two sets A and B, it is the cardinality ratio of $A \cap B$ and $A \cup B$. The Jaccard similarity formula is as follows.

$$J_{\delta(A,B)} = 1 - J(A, B) = \frac{|A \cup B| - |A \cap B|}{|A \cup B|} \quad (2)$$

4.5.4 Levenshtein Distance [KDnugget,(2022)]

The Levenshtein distance is a text similarity metric that measures the distance between words. It has a number of uses, including text auto-completion and auto-correction. In either of these cases, a user's entered word is compared to words in a dictionary to find the closest match, after which a suggestion(s) is made. Because the dictionary may contain thousands of words, the application's response for comparing two terms will most likely be a few milliseconds.

$$\text{lev}_{ab}(i, j) = \begin{cases} \max(i, j) & \text{if } \min(i, j) = 0 \\ \min \begin{cases} \text{lev}_{a,b}(i-1, j) + 1 \\ \text{lev}_{a,b}(i, j-1) + 1 \\ \text{lev}_{a,b}(i-1, j-1) + 1_{(a_i \neq b_j)} \end{cases} & \text{Otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

Where a = String 1, b = String, i = the terminal word portion of String1, J = the terminal word portion of String2.

Typically, the Levenshtein distance is determined by creating a matrix of size (M+1)x(N+1)—where M and N are the lengths of the two words—and looping through it using two for loops, performing various calculations within each iteration.

4.5.5 Evaluation Metrics

We used four measures to evaluate the performance and accuracy of the QA system: Precision, Recall, Accuracy, and Error Percentage. The most commonly used measures in Natural Language Processing are precision and recall. Precision calculates correct and wrong answers, whereas Recall calculates missed values. The precision and recall formulas are as follows:

$$\text{Precision} = \frac{\text{Correct}}{(\text{Correct} + \text{Wrong})} \times 100 \quad (4)$$

For Accuracy measure, it just checks total correct answers with total number of questions asked. The formula is

$$\text{Accuracy} = \frac{\text{No. of Correct Answers}}{\text{Total No. of Questions Asked}} \times 100 \quad (5)$$

Error percentage measure performed on incorrect answers, this is the only measure which performed on irrelevant answers.

$$\text{Error \%} = \frac{\text{No. of Incorrect Answers}}{\text{Total no. of Questions Asked}} \times 100 \quad (6)$$

4.6 Procedure to compare model answer with candidates answers

We have created sixty (60) model question answers. In this experiment, we compared each model answer with forty (40) candidate answers. We have used four similarity measures Sequence matcher percentage, Jaccard similarity, Cosine Similarity, and Levenshtein distance similarity. A procedure described the steps involved for similarity measurement.

Procedure 1:

Step 1: Compare the first model question's answer with the forty candidate answers using similarity measures.

Step 2: Compare the second model question's answer with the forty candidate answers using similarity measures.

Step 3: Compare the third model question's answer with the forty candidate answers using similarity measures.

Step10: Compare the tenth model question's answer with the forty candidate answers using similarity measures.

In Table 4, we have shown the sample of model question No. 5 with forty (40) candidate answers of Class-III Chap- II. In Table 5, we have shown the four-similarity percentages of forty candidate answers with model answers. (Such as Sequence Similarity, Jaccard similarity, Cosine similarity, Levenshtein Distance Similarity)

Model Question: Q. No. 5: मुग्धाच्या आई व बाबा ने शाळेत कोणाची भेट घेतली?

Model Answer: Answer 5: मुग्धाच्या आई व बाबा ने शाळेत बाईची भेट घेतली.

Table 4: Sample of forty candidates answers

Cand	Candidates answer	cand	Candidates answer
C1	मुग्धाच्या आई व बाबा ने शाळेत बाईची भेट घेतली	C21	मुग्धाच्याआई व बाबा ने शाळेत मुग्धाच्या बाईची भेट घेतली
C2	मुग्धाच्या आई व बाबानी बाईची भेट घेतली	C22	मुग्धाच्या आई व बाबा ने शाळेतमुग्धाच्या बाईची भेट घेतली
C3	मुग्धाच्या आई व बाबानी बाईची भेट घेतली	C23	मुग्धाच्या आई व बाबा ने शाळेतमुग्धाच्या बाईची भेट घेतली
C4	मुग्धाच्या आई व बाबा ने बाईची भेट घेतली	C24	मुग्धाच्या आई व बाबा ने शाळेतमुग्धाच्या बाईची भेट घेतली
C5	मुग्धाच्या आई व बाबा ने शाळेतबाईची भेट घेतली	C25	मुग्धाच्या आई व बाबा ने शाळेतमुग्धाच्या बाईची भेट घेतली
C6	मुग्धाच्या आई व बाबा ने शाळेतबाईची भेट घेतली	C26	मुग्धाच्या आई व बाबा ने शाळेतमुग्धाच्या बाईची भेट घेतली
C7	मुग्धाच्या आई व बाबा ने शाळेतबाईची भेट घेतली	C27	मुग्धाच्या आई व बाबा ने शाळेतमुग्धाच्या बाईची भेट घेतली
C8	मुग्धाच्या आई व बाबा ने शाळेतबाईची भेट घेतली	C28	मुग्धाच्या आई व बाबा ने शाळेतमुग्धाच्या बाईची भेट घेतली
C9	मुग्धाच्या आई व बाबा ने शाळेतप्रसिद्ध लेखकाची भेट घेतली	C29	मुग्धाच्या आई व बाबा ने शाळेतमुग्धाच्या बाईची भेट घेतली
c10	मुग्धाच्या आई व बाबा ने मुग्धाच्या बाईची भेट घेतली	C30	मुग्धाच्या आई व बाबा ने शाळेतबाईची भेट घेतली
C11	मुग्धाच्या आई व बाबा ने मुग्धाच्या बाईची भेट घेतली	C31	मुग्धाच्या आई व बाबा ने शाळेतबाईची भेट घेतली
C12	मुग्धाच्या आई व बाबानी प्रमुखपाहुण्याची भेट घेतली	C32	मुग्धाच्या आई व बाबा ने शाळेतबाईची भेट घेतली
C13	मुग्धाच्या आई व बाबानी प्रमुखपाहुण्याची भेट घेतली	C33	मुग्धाच्या आई व बाबा ने शाळेतमुग्धाच्या बाईची भेट घेतली
C14	मुग्धाच्या आई व बाबा ने बाईचीभेट घेतली	C34	मुग्धाच्या आई व बाबा ने शाळेतमुग्धाच्या बाईची भेट घेतली
C15	मुग्धाच्या आई व बाबानी बाईचीभेट घेतली	C35	मुग्धाच्या आई व बाबा ने शाळेतमुग्धाच्या बाईची भेट घेतली
C16	मुग्धाच्या आई व बाबा ने शाळेतमुग्धाच्या बाईची भेट घेतली	C36	मुग्धाच्या आई व बाबा ने शाळेतमुग्धाच्या बाईची भेट घेतली
C17	मुग्धाच्या आई व बाबा ने शाळेतमुग्धाच्या बाईची भेट घेतली	C37	मुग्धाच्या आई व बाबा ने शाळेतमुग्धाच्या बाईची भेट घेतली
C18	मुग्धाच्या आई व बाबा ने शाळेतमुग्धाच्या बाईची भेट घेतली	C38	मुग्धाच्या आई व बाबा ने शाळेतमुग्धाच्या बाईची भेट घेतली
C19	मुग्धाच्या आई व बाबा नेशाळेतबाईची भेट घेतली	C39	मुग्धाच्या आई व बाबा ने शाळेतमुग्धाच्या बाईची भेट घेतली
C20	मुग्धाच्या आई व बाबा ने शाळेतमुग्धाच्या बाईची भेट घेतली	C40	मुग्धाच्या आई व बाबा ने बाईचीभेट घेतली

Table 5: Result of different similarity measures

Cand	1	2	3	4	Cand	1	2	3	4	Cand	1	2	3	4
C1	0.99	0.96	1.00	0.98	C15	0.87	0.84	0.76	0.13	C29	0.87	0.92	0.96	-0.37
C2	0.87	0.84	0.76	0.13	C16	0.87	0.92	0.96	-0.37	C30	0.98	0.92	1.00	0.98
C3	0.87	0.84	0.76	0.13	C17	0.87	0.92	0.96	-0.37	C31	0.98	0.92	1.00	0.98
C4	0.91	0.84	0.94	0.38	C18	0.87	0.92	0.96	-0.37	C32	0.98	0.92	1.00	0.98
C5	0.98	0.92	1.00	0.98	C19	0.97	0.92	1.00	0.94	C33	0.87	0.92	0.96	-0.37
C6	0.98	0.92	1.00	0.98	C20	0.87	0.92	0.96	-0.37	C34	0.87	0.92	0.96	-0.37
C7	0.98	0.92	1.00	0.98	C21	0.87	0.92	0.96	-0.37	C35	0.87	0.92	0.96	-0.37
C8	0.98	0.92	1.00	0.98	C22	0.87	0.92	0.96	-0.37	C36	0.87	0.92	0.96	-0.37
C9	0.83	0.72	0.84	-0.89	C23	0.87	0.92	0.96	-0.37	C37	0.87	0.92	0.96	-0.37
C10	0.85	0.84	0.90	0.12	C24	0.87	0.92	0.96	-0.37	C38	0.87	0.92	0.96	-0.37
C11	0.85	0.84	0.90	0.12	C25	0.87	0.92	0.96	-0.37	C39	0.87	0.92	0.96	-0.37
C12	0.74	0.70	0.59	-0.71	C26	0.87	0.92	0.96	-0.37	C40	0.92	0.88	0.94	0.40
C13	0.74	0.70	0.59	-0.71	C27	0.87	0.92	0.96	-0.37					
C14	0.91	0.84	0.94	0.38	C28	0.87	0.92	0.96	-0.37	AVG	0.89	0.89	0.66	

In above table, We are used some notations such as Cand- candidate, 1- Sequence Similarity, 2-Jaccard similarity, 3-Cosine similarity, 4-Levenshtein Similarity

Table 5 contains the sample of four similarity values for forty candidate answers to one question. There are ten (10) questions in each chapter. We have taken six (06) chapters and four (04) similarity measures. We used four similarity measures, and a total of nine thousand six hundred (9600) similarity values are calculated. Based on these values, we calculated the total correct, wrong and incorrect answers.

5. RESULTS

We considered that, if the similarity value is larger than 0.9 then the candidate's answer is considered a correct answer. If the similarity value is a smaller than 0.5 then the candidate's answer is considered a WRONG answer. The similarity values between 0.5 and 0.9 are considered as INCORRECT answers. Table 6 to Table 13 shows the entire counts of correct answers and wrong answers using Sequence similarity, Jaccard Similarity, Cosine Similarity and Levenshtein Similarity methods.

Table 6: Counts of correct answers

Sequence Matcher Similarity											
	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q5	Q6	Q7	Q8	Q9	Q10	Total
Class II Chap I	1	18	5	11	36	29	32	39	26	35	232
Class II Chap II	40	40	40	40	30	30	5	8	30	0	263
Class III Chap I	40	40	40	0	0	37	0	0	18	40	215
Class III Chap II	40	32	35	38	12	2	39	0	0	39	237
Class IV Chap I	31	40	40	40	11	16	30	38	32	39	317
Class IV Chap II	39	32	37	14	14	16	8	3	33	33	229
Total	191	202	197	143	103	130	114	88	139	186	1493

Table 7: Counts of Wrong answers

Sequence Matcher Similarity											
	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q5	Q6	Q7	Q8	Q9	Q10	Total
Class II Chap I	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
Class II Chap II	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	0	3
Class III Chap I	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Class III Chap II	0	0	0	0	0	23	0	1	1	0	25
Class IV Chap I	0	0	0	0	10	0	0	0	0	0	10
Class IV Chap II	0	0	0	0	1	0	29	0	0	0	30
Total	0	0	2	0	11	23	29	4	1	0	70

From Table 6 and Table 7, we calculated that the total counts of correct answers are 1493, the total counts of wrong answers are 70, and the total count of incorrect answers is 837. We calculated Precision, Accuracy, and Error % using the following formulas discussed in section 4.5.5. The sequence similarity results are precision is 95.52, Accuracy of 62.21, and Error % is 34.88.

Table 8: Counts of correct answers

Jaccard Similarity											
	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q5	Q6	Q7	Q8	Q9	Q10	Total
Class II Chap I	0	1	2	11	39	29	24	39	11	39	195
Class II Chap II	2	2	40	40	2	2	5	8	2	0	103
Class III Chap I	40	6	40	0	0	19	40	13	18	40	216
Class III Chap II	40	31	35	4	29	1	40	1	40	38	259
Class IV Chap I	1	37	40	40	6	16	1	39	38	39	257
Class IV Chap II	39	32	10	14	1	29	8	7	0	0	140
Total	122	109	167	109	77	96	118	107	109	156	1170

Table 9: Counts of Wrong answers

Jaccard Similarity											
	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q5	Q6	Q7	Q8	Q9	Q10	Total
Class II Chap I	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
Class II Chap II	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Class III Chap I	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Class III Chap II	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1
Class IV Chap I	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Class IV Chap II	0	0	0	0	1	0	3	0	0	0	4
Total	0	0	2	0	1	0	3	1	0	0	7

Tables 8 and 9 are shown the total counts of correct answers and wrong answers using Jaccard Similarity. We calculated that the total counts of correct answers are 1170, the total counts of wrong answers are 7, and total counts of incorrect answers are 1223. We calculated Precision, Accuracy, and Error % using the following formulas discussed in section 4.5.5. The sequence similarity results are precision is 99.41, Accuracy of 48.75, and Error % is 50.96.

Table 10: Counts of correct answers

Cosine Similarity											
	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q5	Q6	Q7	Q8	Q9	Q10	Total
Class II Chap I	38	18	2	11	11	39	23	39	25	6	212
Class II Chap II	40	38	40	2	30	38	0	8	30	0	226
Class III Chap I	40	0	0	34	0	18	40	0	22	40	194
Class III Chap II	40	30	35	38	34	2	40	20	40	39	318
Class IV Chap I	0	37	40	40	9	6	31	36	38	37	274
Class IV Chap II	39	32	9	0	14	19	8	5	0	0	126
Total	197	155	126	125	98	122	142	108	155	122	1350

Table 11: Counts of Wrong answers

Cosine Similarity											
	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q5	Q6	Q7	Q8	Q9	Q10	Total
Class II Chap I	0	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3
Class II Chap II	0	0	0	0	0	0	40	8	4	0	52
Class III Chap I	0	0	40	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	41
Class III Chap II	0	0	0	0	0	14	0	6	0	0	20
Class IV Chap I	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1
Class IV Chap II	0	2	2	6	1	0	32	0	0	0	43
Total	0	2	45	6	2	14	72	14	5	0	160

Tables 10 and 11 are shown the total counts of correct answers and wrong answers using Cosine Similarity. We calculated that the total counts of correct answers are 1350, the total counts of wrong answers are 160, and the total count of incorrect answers is 890. We calculated Precision, Accuracy, and Error % using the following formulas discussed in section 4.5.5. The sequence similarity results are precision is 89.40, Accuracy of 56.25, and Error % is 37.08.

Table 12: Counts of correct answers

Levenshtein Similarity											
	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q5	Q6	Q7	Q8	Q9	Q10	Total
Class II Chap I	0	18	2	11	36	29	23	39	9	15	182
Class II Chap II	40	40	0	40	30	38	5	8	30	0	231
Class III Chap I	40	5	40	0	0	17	0	0	17	40	159
Class III Chap II	40	30	10	4	9	0	39	20	40	1	193
Class IV Chap I	23	39	40	40	1	16	0	36	32	38	265
Class IV Chap II	39	32	37	0	14	16	8	1	23	23	193
Total	182	164	129	95	90	116	75	104	151	117	1223

Table 13: Counts of Wrong answers

Levenshtein Similarity											
	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q5	Q6	Q7	Q8	Q9	Q10	Total
Class II Chap I	40	22	38	28	3	10	16	0	13	7	177
Class II Chap II	0	0	0	0	0	2	35	32	10	40	119
Class III Chap I	0	0	0	40	40	3	40	36	22	0	181
Class III Chap II	0	8	5	2	31	40	1	20	0	1	108
Class IV Chap I	16	0	0	0	30	24	6	2	8	1	87
Class IV Chap II	1	8	3	40	26	24	32	37	17	17	205
Total	57	38	46	110	130	103	130	127	70	66	877

Tables 13, and 14 are shown the total counts of correct answers and wrong answers using Levenshtein Similarity. We calculated that the total counts of correct answers are 1223, the total counts of wrong answers are 877, and the total count of incorrect answers is 300. We calculated Precision, Accuracy, and Error % using the following formulas discussed in section 4.5.5. The sequence similarity results are precision is 58.24, Accuracy of 50.96, and Error % is 12.50.

Table 14: Overall Average Result Analysis of Similarity

	Total Answers	Correct Answers	Wrong Answers	Incorrect Answers	Precision	Accuracy	Error %
Sequence Similarity	2400	1493	70	837	95.52	62.21	34.88
Jaccard Similarity	2400	1170	07	1223	99.41	48.75	50.96
Cosine Similarity	2400	1350	160	890	89.40	56.25	37.08
Levenshtein Similarity	2400	1223	877	300	58.24	50.96	12.50
Total	9600	5236	1114	3250	82.46	54.54	33.85

Chart 1: Results of Four Similarity Measures

Chart 2: Results of Precision, Accuracy, Error % Measures

Table 14, Chart 1, Chart 2 shows the overall result analysis of four similarity measures. These similarities are Sequence Similarity, Jaccard Similarity, Cosine Similarity, and Levenshtein Similarity. The total candidate's answers are 9600, correct answers are 5236, wrong answers are 1114 and incorrect answers are 3250. Overall similarity results of four similarities are precision is 82.46, accuracy is 54.54, and error % is 33.85. The results are obtained from Jaccard similarity and sequence similarity.

5. CONCLUSION

The Question answering system plays a very vital role in retrieving the correct responses. Even Question Answering systems are needed in education. Which has been provided during the Covid-19 pandemic as online education becomes the generic way of teaching, learning, and evaluation. Our work concerns the closed domain scenario. During our study, we found that in the Indian scenario, few systems are available in Hindi and a few regional languages like Punjabi, Bengali, Malayalam, etc. but very little research is done in the Marathi language.

In our experiment, Questionnaires are prepared based on the Bhalbharati Marathi textbook of classes II, III, and IV. We have collected nine thousand six hundred (9600) answers from candidates and sixty (60) model answers. We are designing a procedure to test the similarity of model answers and candidate's answers.

We have tested the similarity of the candidate's answer and the model answer similarity measures such as Sequence similarity, Jaccard similarity, Cosine Similarity, and Levenshtein similarity. The total candidate's answers are 9600, out of these total correct answers are 5236, the total wrong answers are 1114 and the total incorrect answers are 3250. Overall similarity results of four similarities are precision 82.46, Accuracy 54.54, and error % 33.85. Our developed model answers are matched to the candidate's answers. So, we decide these candidate's answers are to be considered for the next process of development of the Marathi QA system. We observed that better results are gotten from Jaccard similarity and sequence similarity. In the future, we have to add more chapters and collect more answer data from candidates.

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